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Maintenance 4.0 Framework Using Self-Adaptive Software Architecture

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Abstract

With the recent advances of manufacturing technologies, referred to as Industry 4.0, maintenance approaches have to be developed to fulfill the new demands. The technological complexity associated to Industry 4.0 makes designing maintenance solutions particularly challenging. This paper proposes a novel maintenance framework leveraging principles from self-adaptation and software architecture. The framework was tested in an operational scenario where the vibration of electrical motors in a plant needs to be managed; the results showed a proper operation. As a conclusion, the proposed framework could be used to develop maintenance systems for Industry 4.0.

Keywords: Maintenance 4.0, Maintenance framework, Self-adaptation, Software architecture.

1. Introduction

In today's competitive market, companies strive to adapt new technologies to fulfill customer needs and retain their market share. In the past 200 years three earlier industrial revolutions occurred, driven by mechanization, electrification and information technology respectively [1]–[3]. With the recent technology trend in Cyber Physical Systems (CPS), the Internet of Things (IoT) and the Internet of Services (IoS), a fourth industrial revolution is about to happen named "Industry 4.0". Industry 4.0 is characterized by three main dimensions 1) horizontal integration, which describes the integration of different systems of the manufacturing and business process (e.g. production, logistics, marketing) both within and across several different companies, 2) vertical integration, which describes the integration of the different systems at different hierarchical levels (e.g. sensors and actuators, control system, production management, manufacturing and planning levels) and 3) the horizontal and vertical integration are done through engineering to provide end-to-end solutions [1], [4], [5].

It is widely recognized that maintenance plays an important role to enhance production performance and the sustainability of companies [6]–[8]. With the advances of manufacturing technologies, maintenance approaches changed and developed to fulfill the new demands. Now, with the Industry 4.0, innovative maintenance approaches have to be developed to fulfill the new demands [9], which we refer to as "Maintenance 4.0". This maintenance system should be able to execute the required tasks which include data gathering, monitoring, analyzing,

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planning, executing and data presenting. These tasks should be performed in environment of vertical and horizontal integrated systems with end-to-end engineering solutions. To perform these tasks, Maintenance 4.0 must take into account all of the necessary elements such as sensors, actuators, network, processors, middleware, databases, software and applications.

As software will play an increasing important role in Industry 4.0, Maintenance 4.0 requires a proper software engineering perspective. Research has pointed out that an architectural approach provides the right level of abstraction and generality to facilitate the designing and the modeling of such a system [10]. The architectural approach is concerned with the selection of different abstract elements, as well as defining their interactions and rules in order to achieve system's goal. IBM's self-adaptive based architecture in [11] named MAPE-K (Monitor, Analyze, Plan, Execute-Knowledge) introduced a framework for systems that adapt themselves at the runtime against uncertainties. We claim that this framework could be used to construct a framework of Maintenance 4.0, as it has the necessary elements.

Several researches discussed maintenance methods and systems that are not specific for Industry 4.0 [12]–[18] but they cover some aspects of Maintenance 4.0 such as digitalization, autonomy, intelligence, etc. In lee [19], a framework is proposed for self-aware and self-maintained machines that includes the concepts of cyber- physical system and decision support system. The framework is applied on a case study to demonstrate its feasibility. Bagheri [20] introduced a framework 5C that integrates Cyber Physical Systems in Industry 4.0 environment and analytical methodology using clustering technique to predict failures in machines.

In contrast, in this work we propose a framework for Industry 4.0 maintenance system that considers all of the essential components to complete maintenance tasks. Then we give further elaboration on the mechanisms and the interaction among the components of the proposed framework. This is developed using self-adaptive software architecture.

Hence, the aims of this study are 1) to identify components and sub-components of Maintenance 4.0, 2) to develop a framework for Maintenance 4.0 based on a self-adaptive software architecture, and 3) to model the interaction of Maintenance 4.0 components and sub-components and apply them in an operational scenario.

Next section discusses the self-adaptive software architecture and its advantages. In section 2 we develop framework of Maintenance 4.0. Then in section 3, an operational scenario is established to test the developed framework. The discussion is presented in section 4 and in section 5 the conclusion is drawn.

1.1 Self-adaptive software architecture

Self-adaptive software enables a software system to adapt autonomously with uncertainties (e.g. faults or variation in resources) at run time [21]. In this paper, we consider architecture-based self-adaptation, examples of this approach can be found in [10], [22]–[24]. Mainly, this approach consists of two parts: first a Managed System that is concerned with the working domain and second a Managing System that manages and adapts the Managed System using a feedback loop [21], [25]. Typically, the adaptation process follows a reference model named MAPE-K [11] that represents the components: Monitor, Analyze, Plan, and Execute, which are all connected to Knowledge i.e. a repository. The Knowledge stores the gained data and information such as goals and models of the managed system [21], [24].

In MAPE-K, Monitor monitors the managed system and other relevant information (e.g. environment, operational parameters, etc.), updates the Knowledge accordingly and triggers the Analyzer. Analyzer analyzes the collected data and determines whether an adaptation

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process is required. If so, Plan is triggered to compose a plan with actions that adapt the managed system so it achieves the system goals. These actions are then performed by the Execute [25], [26]. Several researches discuss the benefits of this approach [10], [21]–[23]. In the context of this study we emphasize on the following advantages:

- It provides a foundation for separation of concerns, i.e., each component is responsible for a distinct function. This minimizes the components' interdependency and therefore, simplifies the development, repair and modification.
- The architectural principal covers a wide range of domains. Each domain associated with its specific architecture.
- It provides a level of abstraction that shifts the developers focus from the level of code-lines and algorithmic level to the important system-level compositions. This facilitates system understanding and managing in large complex systems (which might be the case in Industry 4.0).
- It is cost effective as it is based on an external control loop that (in principal) can be utilized by different systems. Developing an internal control system for each new system from scratch would make the system rather expensive.
- It is suitable for systems that respond to changes autonomously at run time.
- It is supported by modeling languages and notations that are describe and reason about the structure and behavior of the system during the design and at runtime.

2. Proposed framework

The term “framework” is used to address complex issues about a domain of interest and convert them into a generic outline. It serves as a template for developing a specific model [27]. The development of the Maintenance 4.0 framework is based on the experience in maintenance and software architecture within our research groups and on the concepts underlying the literature [10], [11], [22]–[24], [27], [28]. The generic components for a proper functional framework of Maintenance 4.0 are considered to be the ones of the MAPE-K reference model, combined with the three- architectural- layers of Kramer and Magee in [10], see also [24]. In Figure 1 the architectural layers are illustrated.

Figure 1: Architectural layers

In this study we added a Mediator layer that enables several machines to be connected (i.e. Managed Systems) and maps them to the Managing System. This will enhance the reusability [23] as well as the scalability. The Managing System contains two sub layers: the Change Management and the Goal Manager. The Change Management is concerned with controlling the Managed System using the MAPE-K loop according to the strategic goals provided by the Goal Manager. To tailor this generic framework to Maintenance 4.0, it is still required to specify the necessary subcomponents, interactions among the components/subcomponents and their triggering conditions.

To that end, the methodology to achieve the Maintenance 4.0 framework was based on three different methods used in [24], [28] and [29]. The methodology consists of three phases. In Phase I, we analyze the tasks that should be performed by Maintenance 4.0 in order to identify the necessary subcomponents. In Phase II, we locate these subcomponents within the MAPE-K framework. In Phase III, we zoom-in on the design and coordination mechanisms of the components and sub-components.

Phase I:

The first essential step to engineer a system for a specified purpose is determining its required tasks. In our previous work in [9] we determined the tasks required to be performed by Maintenance 4.0. In this study we use a top-down analysis approach to analyze these tasks to identify the necessary subcomponents. This step should be done with a great care, as inappropriate selection of subcomponents can lead to undesired effects such as extra costs or components that barely fulfil the demands [29].

The tasks of Maintenance 4.0 are as follow:

- **Condition monitoring:** The system should be able to monitor the assets health in the real time as well as other production elements such as, energy consumption, working environment, operating condition, etc.
- **Abnormalities detection:** It should detect deviations in the assets condition and production process.
- **Diagnose and prognosis:** In case of abnormalities, the system is able to identify the damage and its causes, estimates damage severity and the time remaining.
- **Maintenance planning:** It is able to suggest the most profitable action and time for maintenance associated with the resources and competence required. Also, it should automatically generate the maintenance action schedule to synchronize maintenance actions with production planning.
- **Maintenance execution:** It is able to conduct specific actions autonomic to achieve self-healing assets. For those problems where automatic actions are still impossible from technological point of view, the maintenance system should automatically provide report with the relevant information to conduct the required actions. Also, it should be able to assist maintenance engineers with Augmented Reality (AR) to highlight the way of conducting the action properly.
- **Self-learning:** It can learn from past data to continuously improve and optimize maintenance decisions and actions.

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- Data presentation: The relevant and real-time information, e.g. work progress, machines' condition and their productivity, completed tasks, pending work, etc. should be presented in an easy and meaningful way to the right personals.

Now, we analyze these tasks to identify the relevant subcomponents. In order for the maintenance system to perform the above tasks, the system should be able to collect relevant data to detect abnormalities in the asset's health as well as other production elements. Therefore a subcomponent that collects and stores data required to detect abnormalities is required. Then two subcomponents are needed to identify causes of abnormalities and deterioration of components respectively. Also, subcomponents that determine the severity of a component's abnormality and its health state are required. Two subcomponents were identified for determining mitigation plans and selecting a plan most aligned with the company's goals. To construct and execute the selected plan, the dedicated subcomponent are needed. Finally, two subcomponents were identified for user interaction, i.e., to present data and control the system (e.g. inserting new user goals). In conclusion, the identified subcomponents are: *Update Data, Abnormality Detector, Diagnosis, Predict & Prognosis, Health Evaluator, Severity Evaluator, Possible TACs (Time-Action-Consequence), TAC Selector, Plan Constructor, Execute Plan, Update Manager and User Interface.*

Phase II:

In this phase we allocate each of the identified subcomponents in the generic framework based on their function, see Figure 3. Update Manager and User Interface are located in the Goal Manager. Update Data is located in Monitor. Abnormality Detector, Diagnosis, Prognoses, Health Evaluator, Severity Evaluator and Possible TAC are located in Analyzer. TAC Selector and Plan Constructor are located in Planner and Execute Plan is located in the Executor. An explanation about each of the subcomponents is given as follow:

Update Data: Collects relevant data e.g., process data, CM (Condition Monitoring) of machines, etc. and update the Knowledge.

Abnormality Detector: Detects abnormalities in the production process and asset health using relevant data, e.g., CM, process, performance history, peer machine data, KPI, etc.

Diagnosis: Identifies the abnormality root-causes using data from the Abnormality Detector as well as from other relevant data such as process, performance history, peer machine data, etc.

Prognosis: Estimates the deterioration rate and the remaining life time. The inputs are information from Diagnosis as well as relevant data to machine condition e.g., CM, process, performance history, peer machine data, etc.

Severity Evaluator: Evaluates and ranks the impact of the abnormality on the Managed System and on the company goals. Inputs are from the Diagnosis and Prognosis (the abnormality reasons and types and when it will occur) as well as other information that is relevant to assess the impact e.g., safety, cost, etc.

Health Evaluator: It evaluates the general health state of the Managed System. It must be evaluated regularly, regardless of the abnormality occurrence (i.e., it is not triggered based on abnormality occurrence). The input data are from the severity and other relevant data e.g., deterioration rates CM, production process data, performance history, peer machine data, etc.

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Possible TACs (Time-Action-Consequence): To select the best plan (i.e., its consequences are aligned the most with the strategic goals), all the alternative plans with their consequences must be known. Possible TAC generates all the alternatives and their potential consequences, i.e., the alternative times (T) to make the action (A) and estimates their consequences (C). The inputs are relevant data from the Knowledge e.g., schedules of production, maintenance personal availability, spare parts availability, maintenance actions to be performed, economic data, etc.

TAC Selector: Ranks and then selects the best TAC whose consequences are aligned most with the strategic goals. This is done by using data from Possible TACs and the goals set by the Goal Manager.

Figure 2 Proposed framework of Maintenance 4.0

Plan Constructor: Construct detailed instructions and adaptation steps needed to be performed by the Executor.

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Update: If new strategic goals are inserted to the system by the Goal Manager, the Update imposes them properly, in order to avoid errors and conflict.

User Interface: Provides the end users access to the Managing System in order to change goals or for other reason.

Phase III:

In this phase we design and coordinate the interaction of the components/subcomponents located in the MAPE-K loop only; other extensions are subject of a future work. Figure 3 describes the working activity using activity diagram.

Figure 3 activity diagram of the proposed framework

In order to further elaborate the mechanism of the proposed framework, the next section tests it in an operational scenario; as a real test requires further development.

3. Scenario Implementation

Electrical motors of 75 kW in a plant are managed by the Managing System. In this scenario, a vibration sensor (VS1) is attached to the bearing (B1) of the motor (M1). During rotary motions, the bearings generate characteristic vibrations. Each cause of failure (e.g., imbalance, misalignment, damage in rolling element bearings, etc.) impacts the vibration characteristics, and therefore, information related to the failures could be extracted by analyzing the vibration spectrum [30], [31].

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The Monitor collects and aggregates the data from the B1 and saves it in the Knowledge, then triggers the Analyzer. The spectrum from a measurement at a time (t_0) reveals a serious deviation occurs in the vibration level from the normal value 1.5 mm/s (see Figure 4). The Analyzer detects the abnormality using Abnormality Detector. The Diagnosis is triggered and the relevant data is collected (e.g., environmental, technical records, etc.) to determine the causes of the abnormality. Then Prognosis describes the future behavior of the damage development. For example the damage will proceed due to lack of lubricant in B1 associated with high ambient temperature (which will reduce lubricant viscosity), which will probably increase the wear severity. The Severity Evaluator and Health Evaluator determines the severity of the abnormality as 'Medium' and the current health state of the asset is 75%. Possible TACs determines the possible plans with their consequences. Then the Analyzer triggers the Planner.

TAC Selector, ranks the TACs according to the goals imposed by the Goal Manager, and then, selects the most aligned TAC with the goals. In this scenario, it is to clean and then lubricate the bearing B1 after the completion of the production order 1, which is after 20 day. Then, the Plan Constructor transforms the selected TAC into detailed instructions and steps to be performed and triggers the Executor.

Figure 4 the scenario implementation using activity diagram

The Executor receives the detailed instructions from the Planner. Once the time comes (after 20 days), the execution begins. After completing the maintenance action successfully, the work order is closed.

4. Discussion

Industry 4.0 is characterized by relatively high level of integration among different working areas and therefore designing Maintenance 4.0 in such an environment could be challenging. The proposed framework provides a guideline to start with which simplifies the tasks of designing Maintenance 4.0.

The proposed framework has three main information sources: Condition Monitoring from the machines, the goals and instructions set by the end users through the Goal Manager and the Knowledge (see fig 5). These inputs are utilized to provide three main outputs which are: Maintenance decisions, actions and information to the end users and other working areas.

Figure 5: The Input-Output of the proposed framework

The performance of the framework in the scenario showed a flow that provides all of the necessary information to users and performs the required tasks; this is illustrated in Figure 4. There was no conflict or illogical behavior among the components and subcomponents to be addressed. In general, the performance showed a high interdependency, i.e., the majority of the components/subcomponents trigger the next. However, this could negatively influence the redundancy of the component/subcomponents and therefore should be put in consideration during the design.

The components and subcomponents in general have a great dependency on Knowledge to perform their tasks which emphasizes the importance of common database and data accessibility as promoted by the maintenance concept of Total Quality Maintenance concept [32].

5. Conclusion and future work

In this paper we proposed a framework for Maintenance 4.0 using self-adaptive software architecture. With the technological complexity that comes with in Industry 4.0, designing maintenance system could be challenging. The proposed framework serves as a guide to design Maintenance 4.0. The abstraction of the proposed framework covers different working domain. It is important to note that the subcomponent in the proposed framework are defined basing on their functionality, the technical specification are left to engineers to decide during the design. Future work could include applying other scenarios and apply case

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